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Monitoring of Pink Bollworm (*Pectinophora Gossypiella*) Through Light Trap in Cotton Crop at Tando Allahyar & Matiari District

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Abstract

The study was conducted in two districts, Tando Allahyar and Matiari, to monitor the pink bollworm (*Pectinophora gossypiella*) using the light trap technique on cotton crops at the experimental fields of Taluka Jhando Marri, District Tando Allahyar, Sindh. The study was carried out for three months. During the observation period, the pest was monitored through light traps, and results showed that only the *Pectinophora gossypiella* species was found. The results further revealed the relationship of the pest with different stages of the crop, such as vegetative, flowering, and fruiting stages. In District Tando Allahyar, a greater number of adult moths were captured, particularly during the flowering and fruiting stages of the cotton crop. The catches were recorded as: first fortnight of June (18.62), second fortnight of June (19.50), first fortnight of July (12.50), second fortnight of July (12.37), first fortnight of August (11.37), and second fortnight of August (10.25). The average maximum and minimum temperatures (48°C and 36°C) recorded during 2019 at Taluka Jhando Marri indicated that temperature changes affected the prevailing percentage of insects. The pink bollworm showed consistent activity throughout June, with a noticeable peak during mid-month. Similarly, the study conducted at the experimental field of Taluka Hala, District Matiari, showed that adult moths captured through light traps were: first fortnight of June (18.50), second fortnight of June (18.00), first fortnight of July (16.62), second fortnight of July (16.12), first fortnight of August (13.37), and second fortnight of August (12.37). The average maximum and minimum temperatures (48°C and 30°C) recorded during 2019 at Taluka Hala indicated that temperature variation affected the pest's prevalence.

Keywords: Pink Bollworm; Light Trap; Cotton; Temperature; Monitor

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Introduction

Pakistan is an agro-based economy where agriculture contributes approximately 18.5% to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and employs about 38.5% of the national labour force. In terms of agricultural value addition, cotton holds a position of immense importance, being the second most valuable cash crop of Pakistan, contributing 4.5% to the agricultural GDP and 0.8% to the National GDP. Moreover, cotton serves as a vital source of foreign exchange earnings, underpinning the growth of Pakistan's textile industry. Since both the agricultural and textile sectors depend heavily on cotton, enhancing its productivity remains a matter of national importance. Low cotton yields not only affect growers and traders but also influence textile prices and export competitiveness (Source: <https://gallup.com.pk/intern-publication-3-cotton-production-in-pakistan/>). Pakistan's agrarian economy relies extensively on cotton production, which serves both as a source of rural income and a major contributor to foreign exchange, accounting for nearly 60% of total export earnings. Therefore, efforts are urgently required to increase per-hectare yield through the adoption of modern production technologies. However, the cotton crop remains highly susceptible to insect pest infestations throughout its growing period from the seedling to the picking stage. Among the key insect pests, bollworms are the most destructive, feeding on buds and bolls in all cotton-growing regions (Attique, 1992). Previous studies have reported significant yield losses caused by bollworms, ranging from 30% to 40% (Ahmad, 1980). The potential yield reduction due to insect infestations overall is estimated at 21% (Ali et al., 1982), while specific losses from bollworm

attacks have been documented between 6% and 38% (Bishara and Shakeel, 1982). Among these pests, the pink bollworm (*Pectinophora gossypiella*) has been identified as a major pest of cotton, causing severe damage to fruiting parts and deteriorating the quality of seed cotton. Once the eggs hatch and larvae bore into the bolls, chemical control becomes highly ineffective (Chamberlain et al., 1994). Globally, *Pectinophora gossypiella* has achieved major pest status, becoming one of the most economically devastating pests of cotton (Ghosh, 2001). It has been reported to cause 2.8–61.9% loss in seed cotton yield, 2.1–47.10% reduction in oil content, and 10.70–59.20% loss in normal boll opening (Patil, 2003). Various insect sampling methods have been developed to study pest populations and their seasonal dynamics. Ground-dwelling insects such as Formicidae (ants) and certain Coleoptera (beetles) are commonly sampled through pitfall traps, while low-flying diurnal insects are collected using Malaise traps, and more robust species through sweep nets (Malaise, 1937; Marinoni and Dutra, 1997; Mason and Bordera, 2008; Aguiar and Santos, 2010). However, many insect species are nocturnal and thus remain inaccessible to these conventional methods. Such species are more efficiently captured through light-trapping techniques (Szentkiralyi, 2002). Light trapping has become one of the most common and reliable methods for sampling nocturnal insects and for studying their abundance, diversity, and seasonal flight activity (Szentkiralyi, 2002). Certain species are particularly sensitive to light and can be caught at specific times during the night (Kitching and Cadiou, 2000). Automated light traps, which are self-operating, offer quantitative data on nocturnal insect abundance (Szentkiralyi,

2002). Although light traps may be relatively expensive, they are remarkably efficient in insect collection (Basset et al., 1997; Liu et al., 2007). Insects such as moths navigate using lunar light, maintaining a constant angle to light rays for straight-line flight. When confronted by a closer and brighter light source, they tend to spiral inward and ultimately collide with it (McGavin, 2007). The development of light sources that emit high-intensity UV radiation has greatly enhanced the effectiveness of light traps (McGavin, 2007). Many nocturnal arthropods, particularly insects, are strongly attracted to such artificial light sources (Nag and Nath, 1991; Axmacher and Fiedler, 2004). Light traps employing mercury vapour lamps, gas lamps, or fluorescent UV tubes have therefore been widely used for nocturnal insect sampling (Brehm and Axmacher, 2006). These light-based devices attract insects, which then fall into the collecting chamber, allowing researchers to obtain valuable data on insect distribution, abundance, and seasonal flight patterns (Walkden and Whelan, 1942). Among the various light sources tested, UV and mercury lights capture more insects than incandescent lamps, making them particularly efficient for collecting moths, beetles, bugs, flies, and other active nocturnal insects (Lindquist et al., 1983; Borrer, 1981). With minimal human effort, light trapping can yield a large number of specimens (Holloway et al., 2001; Fiedler and Schulze, 2004), a fact especially true for automatic light traps that require no continuous observation (Southwood and Henderson, 2000). Despite extensive global literature on the use of light traps and the behaviour of *Pectinophora gossypiella*, localized data from Sindh Province, particularly the districts of Tando Allahyar and Matiari,

remain scarce. Given the distinct agro-climatic conditions of these districts, such information is essential for devising targeted pest management strategies. Therefore, the present study was undertaken to monitor the activity pattern of pink bollworm using light traps in these two cotton-growing districts and to analyze its relationship with temperature and crop growth stages under local environmental conditions.

Materials and Methods

The present study was conducted at the experimental area of CABI's Better Cotton Project-Sindh, located in the Tando Allahyar and Matiari districts during the 2019 cotton-growing season. The experiment aimed to monitor adult pink bollworm (*Pectinophora gossypiella*) populations using light traps. The selected research field covered an area of approximately 2 acres in each district. Observations were made daily, and data were pooled for subsequent analysis. The monitoring period extended from 1st June to 31st August 2019. Moth catches were recorded at fortnightly intervals, after which the captured moths were removed from the traps. Simultaneously, maximum and minimum temperatures were recorded to study their correlation with moth activity.

Installation of Light Traps

A total of sixteen (16) light traps were installed at the center of each cotton field (2 acres) to capture adult pink bollworm moths. Each trap was mounted approximately 1 foot above the crop canopy and operated for two hours during the night. The light source used was a solar-powered LED torch with a white-light emission spectrum, producing approximately 250–300 lumens with an effective wavelength range of 400–700 nm. This light source was chosen for its energy efficiency and continuous illumination

capability throughout the trapping period. Each light trap was a funnel-type design, consisting of a light-emitting unit mounted above a transparent conical funnel leading into a collection chamber. The attracted moths, upon approaching the light source, were guided downwards through the funnel into the collecting container, where they were unable to escape. The traps were fabricated using locally available materials following standard entomological trap design principles (similar to [Szentkiralyi, 2002](#)). Captured insects were collected each morning, identified to species level under laboratory conditions, and counted. The data obtained were analyzed to assess the relationship between moth abundance, temperature variation, and crop growth stages during the observation period.

Data collection

The data was collected at 15-day intervals

Results and Discussions

Tando Allahyar

The present study revealed that the population of Pink Bollworm varied with the month of the year. It is evident from the results that, except for June, pink bollworm remained active throughout the month of June. The population in June could be attributed to the climatic conditions and the temperature reached at 48°C during June, and in July, 46°C and August, max 42°C or maybe due to the emergence of moths from the dispensing larvae pink bollworm. Then slowly and gradually the population starts rebuilding up and reaches its peak, a larger one of moth catches 1st Fortnight 18.6 and 2nd Fortnight 19.5 in June 16.37 in July and 12.87 in August respectively.

Table 1: Trap-wise moth catches, Tando Allahyar

Taluka Jhando Marri District Tando Allahyar				
Trap	June	July	August	Tr

#							ap-wis e total
	1st Fortn ight	2nd Fortn ight	1st Fortn ight	2nd Fortn ight	1st Fortn ight	2nd Fortn ight	
Trap 1	20	18	10	12	10	8	78
Trap 2	15	14	12	10	13	8	72
Trap 3	18	25	15	13	8	11	90
Trap 4	21	20	12	15	10	9	87
Trap 5	23	27	10	17	12	13	102
Trap 6	12	15	14	10	15	10	76
Trap 7	19	17	12	9	12	10	79
Trap 8	21	20	15	13	11	13	93
	149	156	100	99	91	82	Total 677
Sum of Fortn ights	305		199		173		
Mont hly Mean Popul ation	19.06		12.43		10.81		

Figure 1: Moth Population Trend Catches Tando Allahyar

Figure 2: Temperature vs Population Trend, Tando Allahyar Matiari

The present study revealed that the population of Pink Bollworm varied with the month of the year. It is evident from the results that, except for June, pink bollworm remained active throughout the month of June. The population in June could be attributed to the climatic conditions and temperature reached at 48°C during June, and in July 46°C and August max 42°C or maybe due to the emergence of moths from the dispensing larvae pink bollworm. Then slowly and gradually the population starts rebuilding up and reaches its peak, a larger one of moth catches 1st Fortnight 18.5 and 2nd Fortnight 18.0 in the month of June 16.62 in July and 13.37 in August respectively.

Table 2: Trap-wise Moth Catches Matiari

Taluka Hala District Matiari							
Trap #	June		July		August		Trap-wise total
	1st Fortnight	2nd Fortnight	1st Fortnight	2nd Fortnight	1st Fortnight	2nd Fortnight	
Trap	15	16	14	18	16	14	93

1							
Trap 2	18	15	12	15	14	12	86
Trap 3	18	15	20	17	11	13	94
Trap 4	20	12	20	18	15	10	95
Trap 5	19	22	17	15	18	12	103
Trap 6	21	27	19	16	11	15	109
Trap 7	17	20	15	16	9	12	89
Trap 8	20	17	16	14	13	11	91
Total	148	144	133	129	107	99	Total: 760
Sum of Fortnights	292		262		206		
Monthly Mean Population	18.25		16.37		12.87		

Figure 3: Moth Population Trend Matiari

Figure 4: Temperature Vs Population

Trend Matiari

Table 3: Average maximum and minimum temperature recorded during 2019 at Taluka Jhando, Marri District, Tando Allahyar and Taluka Hala District, Matiari

Month	Max. temp (°C)	Min. temp (°C)	Month	Max. temp (°C)	Min. temp (°C)
Jun-19	48°	40°	Jun-19	48°	40°
Jul-19	46°	37°	Jul-19	46°	34°
Aug-19	42°	36°	Aug-19	42°	30°

Source: <https://www.accuweather.com/>

A two-way analysis of variance Table 4 revealed significant differences in the mean number of *Pectinophora gossypiella* moths (pink bollworm) captured in traps and fortnights during the 2019 cotton season. The effect of trap location was statistically significant 8.42***, indicating that trap location influenced moth abundance. Similarly, a highly significant difference was observed between fortnights 18.03***, suggesting strong temporal variation in moth captures throughout the season. The interaction effect between trap and fortnight 2.25* was also significant, implying that the influence of trap location varied across sampling periods. This interaction suggests that environmental or crop-stage factors may have differentially influenced trap performance over time.

Table 4. Two-factor ANOVA for moth catches of *Pectinophora gossypiella* across traps and fortnights during the 2019 cotton season.

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P	F crit
Trap	1.760	1	1.760	42.32	.00	95.45
Fortnight	67.84	7	9.691	228.89	<.0001	3.26
Trap * Fortnight	2.25	7	0.321	7.82	0.0001	2.25
Error	38	48	0.792			
Total	109.89	56				

Trap	9	1	2	0	2
Fortnight	5.677	9.135	2461	.04	3231
Error	08	42	14	7	26
Total	7	8	15.62	5193	
	5	4	45		
	1		650.9		
	06	5			

Overall, these results demonstrate that both spatial (trap location) and temporal (two-week period) factors significantly influenced *Pectinophora gossypiella* population dynamics, reflecting the combined influence of the field microenvironment and seasonal variation on moth activity.

Correlation analysis Table 5 revealed a positive and statistically significant association between consecutive fortnights in both districts. In Tando Allahyar, higher correlations were observed between the fortnights of June 2 and July 2 (r = 0.83) and between June 1 and July 2 (r = 0.73), indicating consistent pest population trends at the beginning and mid-season. In contrast, correlations at the end of the season (August fortnight) were weaker, even negative, suggesting a decline or fluctuation in mite activity towards the end of the cotton season.

Table (Annexure A)

Similarly, in Matiari, the trend was less pronounced but still exhibited moderate positive correlations between July 2 and August 2 (r = 0.61), implying similar temporal dynamics. Global trends mark the seasonal variability of *Pectinophora gossypiella*, influenced by climatic and agronomic factors.

Conclusion

There are many sampling techniques of insect collection, active as well as passive. However, Pink Bollworm Adult Moths are collected exclusively through light traps and play an important role in the field sampling of Pink Bollworm Adult Moths populations. Pink Bollworm Adult Moths

capture light trap source and design are highly variable and are affected by a wide range of factors. Therefore, while installing a light trap, environmental conditions, trap design, height of the light source and attraction Hand light torch source must be taken into consideration. The light trap's success depends on the intensity and wavelength of the light source. Most insects are attracted to a particular range of wavelengths. Also, high-voltage light

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Table 5. Pearson Correlation Matrix for Moth Catches

			<i>1st Fortnight</i>	<i>2nd Fortnight</i>	<i>1st Fortnight</i>	<i>2nd Fortnight</i>	<i>1st Fortnight</i>	<i>2nd Fortnight</i>	
Taluka Jhando Marri District Tando Allahyar	June	1st Fortnight	1						
		2nd Fortnight	0.685289	1					
	July	1st Fortnight	-0.38872	-0.04692	1				
		2nd Fortnight	0.734101	0.833072	-0.24927	1			
	August	1st Fortnight	-0.57685	-0.57902	-0.08368	-0.42114	1		
		2nd Fortnight	0.437495	0.678618	0.324337	0.509666	-0.05911	1	
	Taluka Hala District Matiari	June	1st Fortnight	1					
			2nd Fortnight	0.524587	1				
July		1st Fortnight	0.006972	-0.0846	1				
		2nd Fortnight	0.341242	0.162571	0.453091	1			
August		1st Fortnight	-0.3136	-0.38992	0.165302	0.1248	1		
		2nd Fortnight	0.188753	0.447437	0.43422	0.608489	0.097375	1	